

THE ANDALUSIAN NETWORK OF PASTURE-FIREBREAK AREAS

Agroforestry management of firebreaks

1. Ganado caprino en un cortafuegos de Iznalloz, Granada 2. Cortafuegos de la RAPCA, caprino de leche en Iznalloz, Granada 3. Rebaño caprino en un cortafuegos de Iznalloz, Granada 4. Ganado ovino y caprino en una zona de cortafuegos de la RAPCA, Lanjarón, Granada

THE WHAT AND WHY

The Andalusian Network of Pasture-Firebreak Areas (RAPCA) is an initiative developed by the Andalusian Regional Government that combines sustainable forest management with forest fire prevention strategies. RAPCA is made up of a network of livestock farmers who contribute with their herds to the prevention of forest fires through the controlled grazing of firebreak areas, causing discontinuity in the forest masses to prevent the spread of fire.

Its main objective is to maintain and manage firebreak areas through the planned use of grazing, integrating livestock activity as an effective tool for landscape conservation and fire prevention. This network extends throughout Andalusia and is developed in publicly owned forests. It currently covers approximately 14,000 hectares, integrating hundreds of livestock farms.

HOW IS THE CHALLENGE ADDRESSED

Shepherds and livestock keepers are key actors in this model, as they are in charge of guiding the animals in the management of the forest. For this activity, they are paid according to the area they manage, the type of vegetation, the slope, the distance to the sheepfold and the degree of biomass consumption.

Good firebreak maintenance means keeping vegetation under control before the summer arrives. Harvesting in spring should be intensified because, although firebreaks are managed all year round, it is at this time of year that grazing increases.

In order to get the animals to graze on woody substrate, various strategies are used, such as incorporating low fibre feed supplements in the paddocks, or grazing the animals in areas close to the firebreak where the grass is less lignified. The use of GPS collars is also a common practice, which ensures that management is being done over the areas of interest.

Another key issue is related to the livestock species used. These vary according to the type of vegetation and the characteristics of the terrain. In the case studies, there is a mixed sheep-goat herd and a dairy goat herd, whose performance is highly efficient on scrub and the lower part of the mountain area.

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Keywords: Firebreak, Andalusia, Livestock, Pasture, Fire, Prevention, Agroforestry

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ADVANTAGES

The advantages of maintaining firebreak areas through their management with livestock are numerous, and allow this network to achieve the objectives of fire prevention in areas of high environmental fragility, preventing the loss of habitats, maintaining the ecological balance of the systems and their biodiversity, and avoiding the loss and degradation of soils. The RAPCA covers all Andalusian provinces and is integrated in the Andalusian Forest Fire Prevention Plan.

The firebreak areas managed by the network are usually located in strategic high-risk areas, especially in mountainous and forest areas where fires can have devastating effects. This is why livestock play a crucial role to prevent fires in areas with a difficult access. On the other hand, the reduction of vegetation fuel at forest-urban areas is essential from the point of view of major disaster prevention.

In addition to these direct effects on forest systems, livestock farming benefits doubly from this institutional programme, which is coordinated by the Regional Ministry for Sustainability and Environment through the Environment and Water Agency of the Andalusian Regional Government. Firstly, the livestock farmers included in it have an important source of feed for their animals, which is used through extensive or semi-extensive grazing, through annual contracts or pasture use. Secondly, they receive financial compensation for this task of forest management, depending on previously established commitments on the reduction of scrubland and pasture, which acts as an economic complement that affects the profitability of the livestock farms themselves.

The improvement in the socio-economic conditions of the shepherds is reflected in the increase in the rates of rural population settlement, which in turn has another advantage associated with this programme, which is again related to prevention and has to do with the surveillance work carried out by these shepherds, as their continued presence in the territory allows for the early detection of fires.

Finally, it should be noted that these forest management works have a direct effect on the recognition of the work of shepherds and the recovery of traditional uses of the forests.

HIGHLIGHTS:

- **Its main objective is to maintain and manage firebreak areas through the planned use of grazing, thus integrating livestock activity as an effective tool for landscape conservation and fire prevention.**
- **Shepherds and livestock keepers are key actors in this model as they are in charge of guiding the animals in the management of the forest.**
- **The firebreak areas managed by the network are usually located in strategic high-risk areas, especially in mountainous and forest areas where fires can have devastating effects.**

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